

The Thing that Anguishes Us All: The Recurring Social Themes in Edward Albee's Plays

Dr Rose Mary Philip
Assistant Professor
PG Department of English
Alphonsa College, Pala

Orchid Id: <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-0352-6052>

Abstract: Edward Albee is considered one of the four greatest playwrights of American Drama. His oeuvre cannot be pinned down to any one school of thought alone. He has been holding up the mirror against his society through his writing. What distinguished him from other playwrights of this period was his relentless experimentation with the themes that he always dealt with in his plays. Albee has used a wide range of theatrical settings and devices to present realistic and satiric images of human predicament. The paper here attempts to highlight some of his recurring themes that “anguish us all” in his aesthetic of drama throughout his career. Albee proved his competence and skill by writing about something he knows firsthand. Albee’s social protest plays and domestic dramas bring out satiric imbalances in all kinds of relationships in American society, be it between the haves and have-nots or between the Whites and Blacks, between husbands and wives or between parents and children, as in most of his domestic plays.

Keywords: Absurd, Anguish, Experimental plays, Themes

Edward Albee (1928-2016) has always been creatively restless and inventive. Albee has tried to extend the boundaries of drama by experimenting vigorously with its form. His belief that realistic drama had been exhausted and that it was to be modified made him write a play in the form of a dream vision, like a virtual monologue with no actors on stage, as seen in his 1968 play, *Box* and *Quotations from Mao Tse-Tung*. A number of plays followed after that at regular intervals with an innovative spirit which makes them different from his earlier plays. The innovations include expressionistic fantasy as in *Seascape*, Vaudevillian act as in *Counting the Ways*, post-modernism as in *Three Tall Women*, sit-around technique as in *Fragments*, and anthropomorphism as in *The Goat*. But critics failed to understand the innovative spirit and the

complexity of the themes in Albee's plays and so his transition from an Absurdist to an experimental playwright went unnoticed.

The outstanding success of his work *Who's Afraid of Virginia Woolf?* (1962) eclipsed his later plays. He was praised for its technical brilliance. Gerard Weales has inferred that "his pace slackened at the end of the 1960s...Albee never had a critical or popular success to equal—or even to approach—that of *Who's Afraid of Virginia Woolf?*" (417).

The critical environment of Albee's works until *Three Tall Women* (1994) had been rather low. This was mainly because Albee was a playwright who did not want to compromise on artistic instinct for success alone. This is evident from how he treated his critics' unfriendly remarks on *Tiny Alice*. After the play opened on December 29, 1964 at Billy Rose Theatre, New York, many asked Albee to appear to clarify the obscure points in the play. Though Albee appeared for a press meet, he slid away from answering any questions pertaining to the obscurity in the play. He made an author's note regarding this in his published version of the play where he says, "I have decided against creating such a guide for any successes" (1: 21). But critics and the audience failed to take notice of Albee's credibility and integrity towards his works of art; instead they ranked him as a failed Absurdist in the 70s and 80s. Thus, Albee's experimental plays suffered a setback.

However, *Three Tall Women* catapulted Albee back to the forefront of American theatre and after a long period of critical disfavor, Albee was re-recognised. In this play, Albee proved his competence and skill by writing about something he knows firsthand. With this play Albee completed his transition from a playwright of the early sixties to a playwright of the new era. The early nineties gave the right break that Albee had been waiting for twenty years and from then on though his innovative style started to get recognized, he continued to be associated with The Theatre of the Absurd.

Edward Albee in an interview with Digby Diehl discusses his views on what a playwright's style should pertain to:

A man's style as a writer is his voice, the sound he makes--a Playwright's voice is the sound that he makes and the style that he works in doesn't determine them at all. It is something that one catches by ear...The manner and matter determine each other and have nothing to do with the style of a playwright. In other words, what most people think of as style has nothing to do with the style at all. (31)

Based on the above note, one should say that Albee has used a wide range of theatrical 'sounds' and devices to present realistic and satiric images of human predicament. "His satirical thrusts at marriage, public idolization of celebrities, phony friendships, and other subjects that his audiences find hilarious are grounded in a serious view of artist's responsibility" (Dricks 4). Albee's social protest plays and domestic dramas bring out satiric imbalances in all kinds of relationships in American society, be it between the haves and have not's as in *The Zoo Story* or between the Whites and Blacks as in *The Death of Bessie Smith* or between husbands and wives or between parents and children as in most of his domestic plays starting from *The American Dream*.

Albee used his characters as his mouthpieces. Some of them he had taken from his own life. In this connection, an observation made by Mel Gussow in the author's biography, *A Singular Journey* (1999), is quite relevant. Mel Gussow has taken pains to study what made Edward Albee the most heard 'voice' of American theatre in the latter half of the twentieth century. Right from Albee's first play, one could identify his 'voice,' says Gussow. The tale of Peter and Jerry in *The Zoo Story* was a strong wake up call for the world to get oneself involved in life to the maximum. The complacency of American life is exposed here. "Jerry evicts Peter from his Bench" says Philip C. Kolin (24). And Albee in an interview, maintained that Peter is not going to be able to be the same person again. Mel Gussow in Albee's biography has noted that both characters were based on Edward Albee himself as was confessed by the latter. "The two Edwards, the one who lived back in Larchmont and the one who lives in New York City" (ASJ 93). Matthew C. Roudane says that Albee's plays are "alluding to a spiritual malaise that

psychologically anaesthetizes the individual” from completely getting involved with life (“A Critical” 10).

Albee had succeeded in creating satiric caricatures throughout his plays. Through his satires, he attacked “America’s insatiable desire for satisfaction, pleasure and wealth” (Kolin 28). In *American Dream*, Daddy, the docile male lead, tells Mommy, “You just can’t get satisfaction these days” (1: 102). Mommy’s worry over the colour of the hat that she wears in the opening scene of the play makes Daddy pass this as a comment during their casual talk. And this inadvertently points to the reason for American consumerist nature.

Albee’s afterthought on America’s attitude to sexual fidelity is dramatized and satirized in his adapted work of Giles Cooper’s play, *Everything in the Garden*. Albee has fused issues of social relevance with a satirical profundity in this work. Albee stays true to these words of his in the play, “I like catching people in the middle of a laugh and them realizing that it’s not funny--or catching them in the middle of something awful, and realizing that you can’t laugh at it,” (Bottom 239).

Paul Witherington, in an insightful essay, “Albee’s Gothic: The Resonance of Cliché” observes:

Finally, as we pursue the Gothic in Albee, it will be clear that he is a major satirist, and Gothic does not diminish that stance;...Albee’s genius lies in the balance he achieves between satire’s pessimistic cycle and Gothic possibilities of transcendence that are inherent in the grimmest horror (153).

Albee has always dissected families hilariously, be it a relationship between a mother and daughter or a husband and wife. In *Seascape*, the husband and wife exchange their dislike of each other. Albee satirizes their long married relationship as loveless and spiritless on the banks of a romantic beach. Again in *Marriage Play* Albee satirizes the institution of marriage. Jack, the husband, at the outset of the play announces the abandonment of his marriage to the disbelieving ears of his wife, Gillian. And what happens after that becomes one of the biggest revelations on marriage. Whether or not, the husband leaves his wife, he always craves for her companionship.

Death is a prominent theme the female dominated play, *All Over* where death mocks at at the survivors. The Wife in the play is obsessed with how well customs and conventions are going to be observed at her husband's funeral.

The patient onlookers, his adult children, a son and a daughter, his doctor, his Best Friend and nurse, present a mimicry of pretensions, even when death awaits at the door. The theme brings to mind Emily Dickinson's meditation on death "Because I could not stop for Death." The Mistress of the dying man is portrayed as more attentive and emotive than anybody else. In the play, Foster observes, "husbands are remote and inadequate figures of secondary importance" (35). A short lived celebrityhood is satirized in *The Man Who Had Three Arms* (1983) where Albee employs the device of lecture within lecture into a theatrical spectacle about an autobiographical reminiscence by the lead character named, Himself. In the play, Albee explores the vices of celebrityhood and how corrupting it could grow in American society. John Beaufort, reporter to *The Christian Science Monitor* reviews it after being at its first production saying that "it enables the playwright to attack a whole range of targets: from women journalists to interviewers generally, from critics and megabuck promoters to the priesthood" (csmonitor.com). Albee's role as a social commentator and a satirist is most direct in this play. The play had sent waves in critical circle about "an American Everyman," whose tendency was to run behind the shows-off of celebrities rather than appreciating the real talents and achievements.

While receiving the Medal of the Academy of Achievement, in 2005, Albee said to an interviewer:

All art is useful because it tells us more about consciousness. It should engage us into thinking and re-evaluating, re-examining our values to find out whether the stuff we think we've been believing for 20 years still has any validity. Art's got to help us understand that values change. If we've stopped exploring the possibilities of our mind, then we're asleep, and why not just stay asleep? So all art has got to be utilitarian and useful. ("The Academy")

Albee was of the view that theatre and art should have “something to do with the anguish of us all” (SMM 35). He wrote, “Well, if the theatre must bring us only what we can immediately apprehend or comfortably relate to, let us stop going to the theatre entirely; let us play patty-cake with one another, or sit in our rooms and contemplate our paunchy middles” (SMM 5). Albee’s aesthetics was always set to affect the consciousness, which he believed would simultaneously change the social and political character of his audience. Albee’s plays presented a number of social themes which characteristically contributed to the refinement of his audiences’ political stand. Audiences are sometimes puzzled by the lack of resolution in some of his plays. This Albee employs purposefully for his audience to think about the solution of the problem he has presented, be it political or social. As early as in 1962, he wrote, “It is a lazy public which promotes a slothful and irresponsible theatre” (SMM 12).

Edward Albee was convinced, as we have already seen, that art “is to put us in greater contact with ourselves and each other, to question our values, to question the status quo, to make us rethink that which we believe we believe” (SMM 193). His plays indeed addressed the above “Albee-esque” concerns.

However, Albee had an obsession with certain themes that recur in his plays at regular intervals. “Albee is, in a crude sense, a more repetitive playwright than his major contemporaries and near-contemporaries: he returns obsessively to particular images, patterns, structures, and ideas” (Krasner 253).

Though the range of themes that Albee deals with is very impressive, there are certain themes that audiences have often been struck with while watching his plays. Some of them are discussed here. The image of the child, often shadowy, or sometimes fictive as in *The American Dream*, *Who’s Afraid of Virginia Woolf*, *The Play About the Baby* and *The Goat, or Who is Sylvia* always recurs in his plays. Referring to the case of *Who’s Afraid of Virginia Woolf?*, David Krasner says that George, the failed academic, and Martha, the daughter of his college president, get connected to the younger couple, Nick and Honey, because both are childless. Martha thrived on the illusion of an unborn child and Honey has “hysterical pregnancy” fits. The play ends with the

revelation of two truths, first, Honey induces miscarriages in her each time she learns that she is pregnant; second, that George and Martha had their marriage built up on the illusion of an unborn child. *The Play About the Baby* is about a couple who loses their newborn child. In *The Goat*, Billy, son of Stevie and Martin is a troubled kid “damaged by the passions of his parents gone awry” (Dircks 30).

Albee has examined the phenomenon of human loss both in its physical and in its emotional aspects. Death and Life have been two important connecting links referred to in almost all Albee plays. Albee once remarked: “Anyway, there are only two things to write about—life and death” (SMM 131).

The theme of death discussed in *The American Dream* is both realistic and symbolic. It is quite shocking that Daddy and Mommy in the play are interested in adopting their murdered son’s twin brother after twenty years as they found him to be more conforming to their “dream” of a son. In this way Albee ruthlessly portrays the emotional loss of human values of the American middle class psyche through Daddy and Mommy who shed no tears at the loss of their infant son. In *A Delicate Balance*, there occurs a discussion on the death of Teddy, the young son of Agnes and Tobias in whose house the action unfolds. Teddy is fondly remembered as an irreparable loss which has brought about a lot of changes in both Agnes and Tobias’ attitude towards life. As the events unfold in the play, we see how such a personal loss lives through memories, haunts them to the extent of their losing the equilibrium of their life and results in some extreme decisions. Albee’s mid career play, *All Over*, is a continuous meditation on death, loss, and its effects on those left behind. The same is the case with *The Lady from Dubuque*, where the whole play is about how Jo and her husband, Sam, gather together with their couple friends and try to play a group game to ward off death. However, death visits her towards the end of the play.

The lack of proper communication which complicates the relationships is an oft-repeated theme. Jerry in *The Zoo Story* tries hard to establish a relationship with Peter, but fails miserably. In the Death watch play, *All Over*, the final hours of a man bring all the members of the family together, but owing to the brittle relationships that each member of the family shares for one

another, they fail to strike a conversation between themselves. So there is a sense of alienation in the air. In *A Delicate Balance*, Tobias and his daughter find it difficult to strike a warm relationship. In *Me, Myself & I*, Otto and OTTO, the identical twins, have caused many misunderstandings in family due to the lack of proper communication.

The disintegration and failure of the institution of marriage is another recurring theme in many of the Albee plays. One could never meet a perfect couple in any of Albee's plays. The couples, George and Martha in *Who's Afraid of Virginia Woolf?*, Agnes and Tobias in *A Delicate Balance*, Charlie and Nancy in *Seascape*, Abigail and Benjamin in *Finding the Sun*, Stevie and Martin in *The Goat*, are all carrying the burden of married life without any happiness within their relationship. "*Finding the Sun* is like a ballet or a Mozart opera: a round of couplings, recouplings, solos and separation. The themes are marriage and mortality" (Clum 70). Martha is frustrated about George in *Who's Afraid of Virginia Woolf?* for George failed to actualize her father's dreams when they met him during his youth; Agnes in *A Delicate Balance* (1966), being married to Tobias for thirty six years, blames her husband for ceasing sexual relationship with her after the death of her son, Teddy, for fear that another child could bring on another tragedy. In the *Marriage Play*, the words of the husband resonate with the same kind of detached relationship with his wife, Gillian: "We [himself and his wife] stare into the dark and know that nothing is enough, has been enough, could be enough, that there is no way not to have...wasted the light; that the failure is built into us, that the greatest awareness gives to the greatest dark" (3: 303).

"Truth and illusion. Who knows the difference, eh, toots?" (1: 284). This dialogue from the play *Who's Afraid of Virginia Woolf?*, illuminates many facts about Albee's views about life as well as relationships, says Toby Zinnman (41). Further this is one of Albee's important themes in all his plays. Theatrical art is much dependent on both truth and illusion. His characters often try to break forth these false illusions and come out. Sometimes Albee becomes predetermined, through some scenes, some acts, some dialogues etc to blow away the illusion of stage itself by making the audience aware of certain biting realities in life. The direct examination of Truth and

Illusion is best portrayed in *Tiny Alice*. The play analyses how “truth and illusion influence the individual’s religious convictions” (Roudane 74). Albee’s later career play, *The Play About the Baby*, revisits the same theme.

To conclude, Albee’s plays reflected the complex realms of man’s unpredictable self, which, in his opinion, should act as mirrors of individual self-censorship, which is the function of art. All his themes are a reflection of the society in which he dwells. His vision of the purpose and effect of theatre was an antidote to the passivity of people, which leads them to an irresponsible life.

References

Edward, Albee. *At Home at the Zoo*. New York: Dramatists Play Service Inc., 2008.

---. *The Collected Plays of Edward Albee, Vol. 2: 1966-1977*. New York: Overlook Duckworth, 2005.

---. *The Collected Plays of Edward Albee, Vol. 3: 1978-2003*. New York: Overlook Duckworth, 2005.

---. *The Collected Plays of Edward Albee, Vol. 1: 1958-65*. New York: Overlook Duckworth, 2005.

Beaufort, John. “Satiric allegory from Edward Albee: *The Man Who Had Three Arms*.”

Bigsby, C.W.E. *Edward Albee: A Collection of Critical Essays*. Englewood Cliffs, N.J.: Prentice-Hall, 1975.

Bottoms, Stephen. “Borrowed Time: An Interview with Edward Albee.” *The Cambridge Companion to Edward Albee*. Ed. Stephen Bottoms. New York: Cambridge UP, 2005.

Capra, Steve. “Interview with Steve Capra.” *Stretching My Mind*. Edward Albee. New York: Carroll & Graf Publishers, 2006.

Clum, John M. "Withered age and stale custom: Marriage, diminution, and sex in *Tiny Alice, A Delicate Balance* and *Finding the Sun*." *The Cambridge Companion to Edward Albee*. Ed. Stephen Bottoms. New York: Cambridge University Press, 2005.

Diehl, Digby. "Edward Albee Interviewed." *Conversations with Edward Albee*. Ed.

Dircks, Phyllis T. *Edward Albee: A Literary Companion*. North Carolina: McFarland & Company, 2004.

Edward Albee Interview, Biography, Profile." New York: The Academy of Achievement, 14 June, 2018. Accessed on: 27 Feb. 2015.

<https://www.achievement.org/achiever/edward-albee/>.

Edward, Albee. *At Home at the Zoo*. New York: Dramatists Play Service Inc., 2008.

Gussow, Mel. *Edward Albee: A singular Journey*. New York: Applause Books, 2001.

Harold Bloom. New York: Chelsea House, 1987.

Kolin, Philip C. "Albee's Early One-Act plays: A New American Playwright from Whom Much is to be Expected." *The Cambridge Companion to Edward Albee*. Ed. Stephen Bottoms. New York: Cambridge University Press, 2005.

Krasner, David. "Fifteen-Love, Thirty-Love: Edward Albee." *A Companion to the Twentieth Century Drama*. Ed. David Krasner. Malden: Blackwell Publishing, 2005.

Oberg, Arthur K. "Edward Albee: His Language and Imagination." *Prairie Schooner*, vol. 40, no. 2, 1966. www.jstor.org/stable/40629152.

Philip C. Kolin. Jackson and London: Mississippi University Press, 1988.

Play by Edward Albee. Directed by Mr. Albee." *The Christian Monitor*. 14 Apr. 1983.

Accessed on: 19 Aug. 2018. <https://www.csmonitor.com/1983/0414/041401.html>

Roudane, Matthew. *Edward Albee: A Critical Introduction*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2017.